

Parent Feedback Form

2021

MBA

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses indifferent semesters?	50%	50%			
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	30%	20%		
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	50%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%			
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	40%	30%	30%		
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	65%	10%	20%	5%	
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	70%	30%			
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	50%	30%	20%		
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	70%	10%	20%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	20%	10%	

A handwritten signature in purple ink, appearing to be 'Srinivas', written over a horizontal line.

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

Parent Feedback Form

2020

MBA

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	70%	10%	10%		
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	20%	20%	10%	
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	40%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	10%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	40%	20%	10%	10%	
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	30%		
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	20%		
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	60%	20%	20%		

A handwritten signature in purple ink, appearing to be 'S. Allu', written over a horizontal line.

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MANGALORE

Parent Feedback Form

2019

MBA

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses indifferent semesters?	60%	30%	10%		
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	70%	30%			
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	60%	40%			
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	20%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	30%	10%		
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	20%	10%		
7	How do you rate the programs based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	70%	20%	10%		
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	30%	10%		
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	70%	20%	10%		
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	70%	20%	10%		
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	50%	30%	20%		

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DEPARTMENT OF
 TECHNICAL EDUCATION
 TAMIL NADU

Parent Feedback Form

2018

MBA

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	60%	10%	10%	10%	
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	30%	10%	10%	
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	40%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	10%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	40%	20%	10%	10%	
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	65%	10%	20%	5%	
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	50%	30%	20%		
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	70%	10%	20%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	20%	10%	

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Parent Feedback Form

Parent Feedback Form

2017

MBA

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the program that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses indifferent semesters?		100%			
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?		100%			
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?		100%			
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	100%				
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?		100%			
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?		100%			
7	How do you rate the programs based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?		100%			
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	100%				
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?		100%			
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?		100%			
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?			100%		
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?		100%			
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college		100%			

A handwritten signature in purple ink, appearing to be 'A. Srinivas'.

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Chart Title

How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given placements?
system in the College?
achieved from the courses?
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the...
How do you rate the programs based on the
How do rate the courses in terms of
How do you rate the ambience of the college for...
How do you rate the treatment of the students by...
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the
How do you rate the availability of the text and
How do you rate the program that your ward

Parent Feedback Form

2017

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9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	20%		
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	20%	20%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	30%	10%	

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3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	40%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	10%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	40%	20%	10%	10%	
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	30%		
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	20%		
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	60%	20%	20%		

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Question	Dark Grey Bar (%)	Black Bar (%)
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given placements?	20	60
system in the College?	20	60
achieved from the courses?	15	60
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the...	20	70
How do you rate the programmes based on the	20	60
How do rate the courses in terms of	30	60
How do you rate the ambience of the college	40	60
How do you rate the treatment of the students by...	10	70
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the	40	60
How do you rate the availability of the text and	20	50
How do you rate the programme that your ward...	10	70

**Parents feedback analysis
2018
MBA EVENING**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	65	15	5
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	15	40	35	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	60	25	15	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	15	45	15	20
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	30	35	10	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	20	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	20	40	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	40	5	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	20	35	40	0
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	20	30	30	15
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	20	40	15	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	20	25	35	20

**REGISTRAR
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MANGALORE**

SHRI RAM KRISHNA
 HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL
 K. S. ROAD, K. S. ROAD, K. S. ROAD

**Parents feedback analysis
2019
MBA EVENING**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	5	15	50	25	5
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	35	35	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	30	20	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	25	30	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	20	40	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	30	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	30	25	35	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	35	25	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	30	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	10	40	35	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	25	25

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MANGALORE

**Parents feedback analysis
2020
MBA EVENING**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	20	40	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	25	30	30	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	30	20	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	10	30	20	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	20	35	20	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	30	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	35	20	30	15	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	35	25	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	30	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	10	35	40	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	30	20

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MANGALORE**

**Parents feedback analysis
2021
MBA EVENING**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	15	25	30	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	35	30	25	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	15	30	25	25	05
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	25	35	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	20	25	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	35	20	35	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	40	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	35	5
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	15	35	30	20	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	35	15

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MANGALORE**

**Parents feedback analysis
2017
ID**

Parents ' feedback 2017 B.SC-1D

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	30	25	35	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	25	30	25	20	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	35	15	05	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	20	25	35	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	20	40	35	05	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	35	25	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	45	25	5	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	35	10	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	15	35	25	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	15	25	25	25	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	10	35	25	20	10

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MANGALORE**

**Parents feedback analysis
2018
ID**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	65	15	5
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	15	40	35	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	60	25	15	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	15	45	15	20
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	30	35	10	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	20	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	20	40	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	40	5	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	20	35	40	0
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	20	30	30	15
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	20	40	15	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	20	25	35	20

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UNIVERSITY OF
 COLLEGE
 DEPARTMENT

**Parents feedback analysis
2019
ID**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	5	15	50	25	5
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	35	35	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	30	20	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	25	30	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	20	40	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	30	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	30	25	35	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	35	25	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	30	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	10	40	35	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	25	25

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 MANGALORE

**Parents feedback analysis
2020
ID**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	20	40	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	25	30	30	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	30	20	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	10	30	20	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	20	35	20	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	30	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	35	20	30	15	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	35	25	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	30	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	10	35	40	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	30	20

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**Parents feedback analysis
2021
ID**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	15	25	30	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	35	30	25	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	15	30	25	25	05
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	25	35	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	20	25	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	35	20	35	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	40	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	35	5
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	15	35	30	20	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	35	15

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MANGALORE

**Parents feedback analysis
2017
BCom(H)**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	30	25	35	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	25	30	25	20	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	35	15	05	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	20	25	35	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	20	40	35	05	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	35	25	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	45	25	5	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	35	10	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	15	35	25	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	15	25	25	25	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	10	35	25	20	10

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MANGALORE

**Parents feedback analysis
2018
BCom(H)**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	65	15	5
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	15	40	35	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	60	25	15	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	15	45	15	20
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	30	35	10	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	20	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	20	40	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	40	5	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	20	35	40	0
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	20	30	30	15
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	20	40	15	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	20	25	35	20

**REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE**

**Parents feedback analysis
2019
BCom(H)**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	5	15	50	25	5
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	35	35	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	30	20	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	25	30	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	20	40	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	30	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	30	25	35	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	35	25	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	30	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	10	40	35	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	25	25

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MANGALORE

**Parents feedback analysis
2020
BCom(H)**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	20	40	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	25	30	30	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	30	20	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	10	30	20	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	20	35	20	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	30	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	35	20	30	15	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	35	25	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	30	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	10	35	40	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	30	20

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MANGALORE**

**Parents feedback analysis
2021
BCom(H)**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	15	25	30	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	35	30	25	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	15	30	25	25	05
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	25	35	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	20	25	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	35	20	35	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	40	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	35	5
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	15	35	30	20	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	35	15

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MANGALORE

**Parents feedback analysis
2017
BCom(CA)**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	30	25	35	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	25	30	25	20	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	35	15	05	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	20	25	35	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	20	40	35	05	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	35	25	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	45	25	5	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	35	10	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	15	35	25	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	15	25	25	25	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	10	35	25	20	10

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**Parents feedback analysis
2018
BCom(CA)**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	65	15	5
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	15	40	35	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	60	25	15	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	15	45	15	20
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	30	35	10	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	20	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	20	40	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	40	5	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	20	35	40	0
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	20	30	30	15
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	20	40	15	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	20	25	35	20

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MANGALORE

**Parents feedback analysis
2019
BCom(CA)**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	5	15	50	25	5
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	35	35	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	30	20	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	25	30	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	20	40	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	30	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	30	25	35	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	35	25	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	30	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	10	40	35	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	25	25

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MANGALORE

**Parents feedback analysis
2020
BCom(CA)**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	20	40	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	25	30	30	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	30	20	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	10	30	20	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	20	35	20	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	30	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	35	20	30	15	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	35	25	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	30	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	10	35	40	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	30	20

A handwritten signature in purple ink, appearing to be 'A. Srinivas', written over a horizontal line.

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MANGALORE**

**Parents feedback analysis
2021
BCom(CA)**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	15	25	30	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	35	30	25	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	15	30	25	25	05
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	25	35	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	20	25	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	35	20	35	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	40	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	35	5
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	15	35	30	20	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	35	15

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MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis
2018
MCom

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2019
MCom

Parents ' feedback 2019	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	70%	16%	5%	5%	4%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	75%	20%	5%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	10%	20%	10%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	5%	5%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	45%	20%	10%	10%	15%

**REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE**

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2020
MCom

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	80%	5%	5%	5%	5%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	70%	10%	0%	10%	10%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do you rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	70%	10%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	60%	20%	5%	5%	10%

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

100%
 90%
 80%
 70%
 60%
 50%
 40%
 30%
 20%
 10%
 0%

Parents feedback analysis
2021
MCom

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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 MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

**SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY**

Parents feedback analysis
2021
BSW

Parents ' feedback 2020-21	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

**REGISTRAR
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MANGALORE**

Parents feedback

REC'D
GRINIVA
MAY 2018

**Parents feedback analysis
2017
MSW**

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

**REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE**

Parents feedback analysis

UNIVERSITY OF...
 DEPARTMENT OF...
 2024

Parents feedback analysis
2018
MSW

Parents ' feedback 2018	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	70%	16%	5%	5%	4%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	75%	20%	5%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	10%	20%	10%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	5%	5%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	45%	20%	10%	10%	15%

 REGISTRAR
 SRINIVAS
 MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2019
MSW

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	80%	5%	5%	5%	5%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	70%	10%	0%	10%	10%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	70%	10%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	60%	20%	5%	5%	10%

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

SRINIVAS ENGINEERING COLLEGE
 SRINIVAS ENGINEERING COLLEGE
 SRINIVAS ENGINEERING COLLEGE

Parents feedback analysis
2020
MSW

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

REGISTERED
 SHRIWAS UNIVERSITY
 MANGALURU

Parents feedback analysis
2021
MSW

Parents ' feedback 2020-21	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

 REGISTRAR
 SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
 MANASA

**SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY**

Parents feedback analysis
2020
BAJ

Parents ' feedback 2020-21	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?					
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?					
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	90%	10%	0%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?					
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?					
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?					
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college					

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

Chart Title

REGISTRAR
SRINIVASA UNIVERSITY
MADHURAI

Parents feedback analysis
2021
BA J

Parents ' feedback 2020-21	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?					
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?					
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	90%	10%	0%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?					
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?					
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?					
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college					

 REGISTRATION
 SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
 MANGALORE

Chart Title

**Parents feedback analysis
2017
BCA**

Parents ' feedback 2017 BCA	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

**REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE**

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2018
BCA

Parents ' feedback 2018	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	70%	16%	5%	5%	4%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	75%	20%	5%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	10%	20%	10%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	5%	5%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	45%	20%	10%	10%	15%

 REGISTRAR
 SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
 MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2019
BCA

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	80%	5%	5%	5%	5%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	70%	10%	0%	10%	10%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do you rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	70%	10%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	60%	20%	5%	5%	10%

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

CHINIA'S UNIVERSITY
 HONG KONG

Parents feedback analysis
2020
BCA

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

 REGISTRAR
 SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
 MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

SRI JAYACHANDRAN COLLEGE OF ARTS AND SCIENCE

Parents feedback analysis
2021
BCA

Parents ' feedback 2020-21	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis

2017

MCA L

Parents Feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	64	17	4
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	24	35	32	9	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	66	23	11	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	0	15	18	45	22
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	26	35	39	0	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	10	25	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	18	35	40	7	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	18	28	45	4
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	2	21	25	35	17
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	18	38	30	14	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	12	18	40	30

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2018
MCA L

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2019
MCA L

Parents ' feedback 2019	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	70%	16%	5%	5%	4%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	75%	20%	5%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	10%	20%	10%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	5%	5%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	45%	20%	10%	10%	15%

**REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE**

Parents feedback analysis

**Parents feedback analysis
2020
MCA L**

Parents Feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	64	17	4
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	24	35	32	9	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	66	23	11	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	0	15	18	45	22
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	26	35	39	0	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	10	25	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	18	35	40	7	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	18	28	45	4
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	2	21	25	35	17
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	18	38	30	14	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	12	18	40	30

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Parents feedback analysis

REGISTRATION
SHRINIVAS

Parents feedback analysis
2021
MCA L

Parents Feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	64	17	4
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	24	35	32	9	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	66	23	11	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	0	15	18	45	22
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	26	35	39	0	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	10	25	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	18	35	40	7	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	18	28	45	4
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	2	21	25	35	17
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	18	38	30	14	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	12	18	40	30

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis
2017
BTech Cs

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2018
BTech Cs

Parents ' feedback 2018	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	70%	16%	5%	5%	4%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	75%	20%	5%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	10%	20%	10%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	5%	5%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	45%	20%	10%	10%	15%

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2019
BTech Cs

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	80%	5%	5%	5%	5%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	70%	10%	0%	10%	10%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do you rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	70%	10%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	60%	20%	5%	5%	10%

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis
2020
BTech Cs

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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 SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY,
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Parents feedback analysis

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Parents feedback analysis
2021
BTech Cs

Parents ' feedback 2020-21	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
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How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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 SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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Parents feedback

**Parents feedback analysis
2017
BTech EC**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
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How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2018
BTech EC

Parents ' feedback 2018	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	70%	16%	5%	5%	4%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	75%	20%	5%	0%	0%
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How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	45%	20%	10%	10%	15%

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Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2019
BTech EC

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How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	80%	5%	5%	5%	5%
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How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
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How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	60%	20%	5%	5%	10%

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MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis
2020
BTech EC

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How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
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How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2021
BTech EC

Parents ' feedback 2020-21	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
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How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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 MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2017
BTech CV

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
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How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

LIBRARY
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2023

Parents feedback analysis
2018
BTech CV

Parents ' feedback 2018	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	70%	16%	5%	5%	4%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	75%	20%	5%	0%	0%
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How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
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How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	10%	20%	10%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	5%	5%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	45%	20%	10%	10%	15%

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MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2019
BTech CV

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	80%	5%	5%	5%	5%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	70%	10%	0%	10%	10%
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How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	70%	10%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
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How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	60%	20%	5%	5%	10%

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MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis
2020
BTech CV

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
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How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis

2021

BTech CV

Parents ' feedback 2020-21	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
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How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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MANGALURU

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2017
BTech Mech

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
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How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

**Parents feedback analysis
2018
BTech Mech**

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How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	70%	16%	5%	5%	4%
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MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2019
BTech Mech

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
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Parents feedback analysis
2020
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Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do you rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis

2021

BTech Mech

Parents ' feedback 2020-21	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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**Parents feedback analysis
2020
BTech AI & ML**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	30	25	35	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	35	45	15	05	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	30	25	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	35	35	05	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	25	30	25	20	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	20	40	35	5	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	25	45	10	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	30	25	20	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	10	25	35	20	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	30	30	30	10	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	20	25	25	20	10

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Parents feedback analysis

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**Parents feedback analysis
2021
BTech AI & ML**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	15	25	30	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	10	30	45	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	25	45	25	05	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	15	30	25	25	05
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	35	25	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	25	25	35	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	25	25	20	20	10
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	30	35	25	5
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	30	35	20	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	20	25	35	15	5

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Parents feedback analysis

**Parents feedback analysis
2017
MTech Cv**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	35	45	15	5
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	35	25	35	5	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	75	15	10	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	0	15	35	30	20
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	35	40	05	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	10	40	25	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	45	25	5	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	15	35	45	5	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	40	25	25	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	20	25	35	15
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	20	40	30	10	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	30	30	30	10

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MANGALORE**

Parents feedback analysis

**Parents feedback analysis
2018
MTech Cv**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	5	35	20	40	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	30	20	35	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	60	30	10	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	0	15	35	30	20
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	20	40	35	05	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	30	30	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	40	30	5	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	15	35	40	10	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	15	30	30	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	10	25	30	25	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	25	30	35	10	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	10	35	25	25	05

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Parents feedback analysis

**Parents feedback analysis
2019
MTech Cv**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	30	25	35	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	25	30	25	20	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	35	15	05	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	20	25	35	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	20	40	35	05	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	35	25	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	45	25	5	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	35	10	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	15	35	25	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	15	25	25	25	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	10	35	25	20	10

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Parents feedback analysis

**Parents feedback analysis
2020
MTech Cv**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	30	25	35	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	35	45	15	05	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	30	25	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	35	35	05	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	25	30	25	20	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	20	40	35	5	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	25	45	10	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	30	25	20	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	10	25	35	20	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	30	30	30	10	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	20	25	25	20	10

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Parents feedback analysis

**Parents feedback analysis
2021
MTech Cv**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	15	25	30	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	10	30	45	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	25	45	25	05	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	15	30	25	25	05
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	35	25	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	25	25	35	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	25	25	20	20	10
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	30	35	25	5
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	30	35	20	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	20	25	35	15	5

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MANGALURU**

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis

2017

MTech Cs

Parents ' feedback 2017	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis

2018

MTech Cs

Parents ' feedback 2018	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	70%	16%	5%	5%	4%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	75%	20%	5%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	10%	20%	10%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	5%	5%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	45%	20%	10%	10%	15%

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Chart Title

Parents feedback analysis

2019

MTech Cs

Parents ' feedback 2019	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	80%	5%	5%	5%	5%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	70%	10%	0%	10%	10%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	70%	10%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	60%	20%	5%	5%	10%

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Parents feedback analysis

2020

MTech Cs

Parents ' feedback 2020	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and referencebooks in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the coursesincluded into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching andevaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effectivedelivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to thelatest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort ofyour ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in theInstitution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward hasachieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluationsystem in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your wardin getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after thecompletion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given toyour ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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Parents feedback analysis

2021

MTech CS

Parents ' feedback 2021	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	55%	14%	15%	10%	6%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	75%	20%	5%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	72%	18%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	65%	20%	5%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	66%	24%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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Parents feedback analysis

Parent Feedback Form

2017

BSc MIT

How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	70%	10%	10%	0%	
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	40%	10%	0%	
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	50%	30%	10%	0%	
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	20%	10%		
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	50%	20%	20%	10%	
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	65%	10%	20%	5%	
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	50%	30%	20%		
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	70%	10%	20%		
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	50%	20%	20%	10%	

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Chart Title

**Parent Feedback Form
2018
BSc MIT**

How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	75%	10%	15%	0%	
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	50%	0%	0%	
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	50%	30%	10%	10%	
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	0%		
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	65%	10%	20%	5%	
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	50%	30%	20%		
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	20%	0%	
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	70%	30%	0%		
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	50%	20%	20%	10%	

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Chart Title

Parent Feedback Form

2019

BSc MIT

How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	70%	10%	10%	0%	
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	40%	10%	0%	
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	50%	30%	10%	0%	
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	20%	10%		
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	50%	20%	20%	10%	
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	65%	10%	20%	5%	
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	50%	30%	20%		
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	70%	10%	20%		
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	50%	20%	20%	10%	

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Chart Title

**Parent Feedback Form
2020
BSc MIT**

How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	75%	10%	15%	0%	
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	50%	0%	0%	
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	50%	30%	10%	10%	
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	0%		
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	65%	10%	20%	5%	
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	50%	30%	20%		
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	20%	0%	
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	70%	30%	0%		
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	50%	20%	20%	10%	

 REGISTERED
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
 MANGALORE

Chart Title

Parent Feedback Form

2021

BSc MIT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	60%	10%	10%	10%	
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	30%	10%	10%	
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	40%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	10%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	40%	20%	10%	10%	
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	65%	10%	20%	5%	
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	50%	30%	20%		
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	70%	10%	20%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	20%	10%	

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MANGALORE

Parent Feedback Form

**SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY**

Parent Feedback Form

2017

BSc CVT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses indifferent semesters?	50%	50%			
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	30%	20%		
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	50%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%			
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	40%	30%	30%		
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	65%	10%	20%	5%	
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	70%	30%			
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	50%	30%	20%		
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	70%	10%	20%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	20%	10%	

**REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE**

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Parent Feedback Form

2018

BSc CVT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	70%	10%	10%		
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	20%	20%	10%	
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	40%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	10%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	40%	20%	10%	10%	
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	30%		
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	20%		
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	60%	20%	20%		

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MANGALORE

Parent Feedback Form

2019

BSc CVT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses indifferent semesters?	60%	30%	10%		
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	70%	30%			
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	60%	40%			
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	20%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	30%	10%		
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	20%	10%		
7	How do you rate the programs based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	70%	20%	10%		
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	30%	10%		
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	70%	20%	10%		
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	70%	20%	10%		
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	50%	30%	20%		

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MANGALORE

Parent Feedback Form

2020

BSc CVT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	60%	10%	10%	10%	
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	30%	10%	10%	
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	40%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	10%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	40%	20%	10%	10%	
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	65%	10%	20%	5%	
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	50%	30%	20%		
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	70%	10%	20%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	20%	10%	

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MANGALORE

Parent Feedback Form

Parent Feedback Form

2021

BSc CVT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the program that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses indifferent semesters?		100%			
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?		100%			
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?		100%			
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	100%				
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?		100%			
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?		100%			
7	How do you rate the programs based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?		100%			
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	100%				
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?		100%			
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?		100%			
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?			100%		
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?		100%			
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college		100%			

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MANGALORE

Chart Title

Parent Feedback Form

2017

BSc RT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	70%	10%	10%		
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	20%	20%	10%	
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	40%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	10%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	40%	20%	10%	10%	
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	30%		
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	20%		
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	60%	20%	20%		

A handwritten signature in purple ink, appearing to read 'Allu'.

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MANGALORE

Parent Feedback Form

2018

BSc RT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	60%	10%	10%	10%	
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	30%	10%	10%	
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	40%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	10%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	40%	20%	10%	10%	
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	65%	10%	20%	5%	
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	50%	30%	20%		
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	70%	10%	20%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	20%	10%	

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Parent Feedback Form

Parent Feedback Form

2019

BSc RT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	70%	10%	10%		
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	20%	20%	10%	
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	40%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	10%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	40%	20%	10%	10%	
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	30%		
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	20%		
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	20%	10%	

A handwritten signature in purple ink, appearing to be 'A. Srinivas'.

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

Parent Feedback Form

2020

BSc RT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	70%	10%	10%		
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	20%	20%		
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	40%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	10%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	50%	30%	10%		
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	30%		
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	20%		
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	20%		
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	20%	20%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	30%	10%	

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MANGALORE

Parent Feedback Form

2021

BSc RT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	70%	10%	10%		
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	20%	20%	10%	
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	40%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	10%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	40%	20%	10%	10%	
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	30%		
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	20%		
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	60%	20%	20%		

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

**Parents feedback analysis
2017
BSc MLT**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	30	25	35	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	25	30	25	20	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	35	15	05	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	20	25	35	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	20	40	35	05	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	35	25	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	45	25	5	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	35	10	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	15	35	25	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	15	25	25	25	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	10	35	25	20	10

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MANGALORE

**Parents feedback analysis
2018
BSc MLT**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	65	15	5
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	15	40	35	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	60	25	15	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	15	45	15	20
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	30	35	10	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	20	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	20	40	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	40	5	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	20	35	40	0
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	20	30	30	15
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	20	40	15	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	20	25	35	20

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 MANGALORE

**Parents feedback analysis
2019
BSc MLT**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	5	15	50	25	5
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	35	35	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	30	20	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	25	30	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	20	40	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	30	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	30	25	35	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	35	25	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	30	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	10	40	35	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	25	25

**REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE**

**Parents feedback analysis
2020
BSc MLT**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	20	40	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	25	30	30	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	30	20	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	10	30	20	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	20	35	20	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	30	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	35	20	30	15	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	35	25	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	30	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	10	35	40	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	30	20

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

**Parents feedback analysis
2021
BSc MLT**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	65	15	5
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	15	40	35	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	60	25	15	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	15	45	15	20
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	30	35	10	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	20	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	20	40	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	40	5	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	20	35	40	0
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	20	30	30	15
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	20	40	15	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	20	25	35	20

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MANGALORE**

**Parents feedback analysis
2017
BSc RDT**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	5	15	50	25	5
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	35	35	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	30	20	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	25	30	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	20	40	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	30	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	30	25	35	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	35	25	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	30	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	10	40	35	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	25	25

 REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY,
 MANGALORE

**Parents feedback analysis
2018
BSc RDT**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	20	40	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	25	30	30	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	30	20	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	10	30	20	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	20	35	20	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	30	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	35	20	30	15	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	35	25	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	30	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	10	35	40	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	30	20

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**Parents feedback analysis
2019
BSc RDT**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	15	25	30	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	35	30	25	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	15	30	25	25	05
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	25	35	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	20	25	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	35	20	35	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	40	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	35	5
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	15	35	30	20	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	35	15

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MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis
2020
BSc RDT

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	30	25	35	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	25	30	25	20	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	35	15	05	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	20	25	35	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	20	40	35	05	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	35	25	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	45	25	5	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	35	10	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	15	35	25	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	15	25	25	25	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	10	35	25	20	10

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MANGALORE

**Parents feedback analysis
2021**

BSc RDT

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	65	15	5
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	15	40	35	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	60	25	15	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	15	45	15	20
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	30	35	10	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	20	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	20	40	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	40	5	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	20	35	40	0
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	20	30	30	15
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	20	40	15	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	20	25	35	20

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**Parents feedback analysis
2017
BSc PT**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	5	15	50	25	5
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	35	35	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	30	20	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	25	30	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	20	40	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	30	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	30	25	35	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	35	25	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	30	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	10	40	35	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	25	25

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**Parents feedback analysis
2018
BSc PT**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	20	40	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	25	30	30	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	30	20	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	10	30	20	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	20	35	20	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	30	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	35	20	30	15	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	35	25	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	30	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	10	35	40	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	30	20

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**Parents feedback analysis
2019
BSc PT**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	15	25	30	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	35	30	25	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	15	30	25	25	05
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	25	35	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	20	25	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	35	20	35	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	40	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	35	5
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	15	35	30	20	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	35	15

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**Parents feedback analysis
2020
BSc PT**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	30	25	35	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	25	30	25	20	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	35	15	05	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	20	25	35	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	20	40	35	05	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	35	25	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	45	25	5	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	35	10	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	15	35	25	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	15	25	25	25	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	10	35	25	20	10

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**Parents feedback analysis
2021
BSc PT**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	65	15	5
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	15	40	35	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	60	25	15	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	15	45	15	20
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	30	35	10	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	20	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	20	40	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	40	5	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	20	35	40	0
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	20	30	30	15
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	20	40	15	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	20	25	35	20

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MANGALORE**

**Parents feedback analysis
2017
BSc APT**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	5	15	50	25	5
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	35	35	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	30	20	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	25	30	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	20	40	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	30	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	30	25	35	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	35	25	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	30	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	10	40	35	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	25	25

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**Parents feedback analysis
2018
BSc APT**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	20	40	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	25	30	30	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	30	20	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	10	30	20	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	20	35	20	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	30	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	35	20	30	15	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	35	25	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	30	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	10	35	40	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	30	20

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**Parents feedback analysis
2019
BSc APT**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	15	25	30	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	35	30	25	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	15	30	25	25	05
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	25	35	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	20	25	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	35	20	35	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	40	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	35	5
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	15	35	30	20	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	35	15

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**Parents feedback analysis
2020
BSc APT**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	30	25	35	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	25	30	25	20	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	35	15	05	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	20	25	35	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	20	40	35	05	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	35	25	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	45	25	5	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	35	10	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	15	35	25	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	15	25	25	25	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	10	35	25	20	10

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MANGALORE**

**Parents feedback analysis
2021
BSc APT**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	65	15	5
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	15	40	35	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	60	25	15	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	15	45	15	20
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	30	35	10	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	20	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	20	40	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	40	5	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	20	35	40	0
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	20	30	30	15
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	20	40	15	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	20	25	35	20

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MANGALORE**

**Parents feedback analysis
2017
BSc O**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	5	15	50	25	5
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	35	35	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	30	20	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	5	25	30	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	20	40	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	30	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	30	25	35	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	35	25	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	30	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	10	40	35	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	25	25

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**Parents feedback analysis
2018
BSc O**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	20	40	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	25	30	30	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	45	30	20	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	10	30	20	25	15
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	20	35	20	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	15	30	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	35	20	30	15	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	35	25	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	30	10
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	10	35	40	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	30	20

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**Parents feedback analysis
2019
BSc O**

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	15	25	30	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	35	30	25	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	15	30	25	25	05
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	25	35	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	20	25	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	35	20	35	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	40	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	35	5
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	15	35	30	20	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	35	15

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Parents feedback analysis
2020
BSc O

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2021
BSc O

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	70%	16%	5%	5%	4%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	75%	20%	5%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do you rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	10%	20%	10%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	5%	5%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	45%	20%	10%	10%	15%

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Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2018
BSc FS

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?					
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?					
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	90%	10%	0%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?					
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?					
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?					
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college					

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 SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
 MANGALORE

Chart Title

**Parents feedback analysis
2019
BSc FS**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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 MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2020
BSc FS

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	70%	16%	5%	5%	4%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	75%	20%	5%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	10%	20%	10%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	5%	5%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	45%	20%	10%	10%	15%

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
 BANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2021
BSc FS

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	80%	5%	5%	5%	5%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	70%	10%	0%	10%	10%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	70%	10%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	60%	20%	5%	5%	10%

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MANGALURU

Parents feedback analysis
2019
BSc CCT

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2020
BSc CCT

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

 REGISTRAR
 SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
 MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

**Parents feedback analysis
2021
BSc CCT**

Parents Feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	64	17	4
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	24	35	32	9	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	66	23	11	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	0	15	18	45	22
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	26	35	39	0	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	10	25	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	18	35	40	7	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	18	28	45	4
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	2	21	25	35	17
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	18	38	30	14	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	12	18	40	30

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Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2020
BSc DCFS

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2021
BSc DCFS

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	70%	16%	5%	5%	4%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	75%	20%	5%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	10%	20%	10%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	5%	5%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	45%	20%	10%	10%	15%

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MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

**Parents feedback analysis
2020
BSc CP**

Parents Feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	64	17	4
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	24	35	32	9	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	66	23	11	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	0	15	18	45	22
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	26	35	39	0	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	10	25	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	18	35	40	7	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	18	28	45	4
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	2	21	25	35	17
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	18	38	30	14	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	12	18	40	30

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MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

2021

BSc CP

Parents Feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	64	17	4
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	24	35	32	9	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	66	23	11	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	0	15	18	45	22
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	26	35	39	0	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	10	25	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	18	35	40	7	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	18	28	45	4
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	2	21	25	35	17
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	18	38	30	14	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	12	18	40	30

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Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2020
BSc IV

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and referencebooks in the market?	70%	16%	5%	5%	4%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the coursesincluded into the curriculum?	75%	20%	5%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching andevaluation?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effectivedelivery of the academic process?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to thelatest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort ofyour ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in theInstitution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward hasachieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluationsystem in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your wardin getting jobs and placements?	60%	10%	20%	10%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after thecompletion of the course?	60%	30%	5%	5%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given toyour ward by the college	45%	20%	10%	10%	15%

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Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2021
BSc IV

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	80%	5%	5%	5%	5%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	70%	10%	0%	10%	10%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	70%	10%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	60%	20%	5%	5%	10%

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Parents feedback analysis
2020
M.Sc. FS

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

 REGISTRAR
 SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
 MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2021
M.Sc. FS

Parents ' feedback 2020-21	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

 REGISTRAR
 SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
 MANGALORE

Parents feedback

Parents feedback analysis
2020
M.Sc. FSC

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2021
M.Sc. FSC

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	70%	16%	5%	5%	4%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	75%	20%	5%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	65%	20%	10%	5%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	10%	20%	10%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	5%	5%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	45%	20%	10%	10%	15%

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2020
MSc CS

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	80%	5%	5%	5%	5%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	70%	10%	0%	10%	10%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	70%	10%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	60%	20%	5%	5%	10%

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis
2021
MSc CS

Parents ' feedback	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and referencebooks in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the coursesincluded into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching andevaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effectivedelivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to thelatest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort ofyour ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in theInstitution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward hasachieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluationsystem in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your wardin getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after thecompletion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given toyour ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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 SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
 MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2020
MSc CP

Parents ' feedback 2020	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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 SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
 MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis
2021
M.Sc. CP

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	12%	10%	10%	8%
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	80%	20%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	20%	20%	0%	0%
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	30%	0%	0%	0%
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	10%	10%	0%
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	10%	5%	5%
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	10%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	50%	10%	20%	20%	0%
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	10%	10%	20%

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MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

Parent Feedback Form

2017

BPT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	70%	10%	10%		
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	20%	20%	10%	
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	40%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	10%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	40%	20%	10%	10%	
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	30%		
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	20%		
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	20%	10%	

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**Parent Feedback Form
2018
BPT**

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	60%	10%	10%	10%	
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	30%	10%	10%	
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	40%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	10%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	40%	20%	10%	10%	
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	65%	10%	20%	5%	
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	50%	30%	20%		
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	70%	10%	20%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	20%	10%	

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MANGALORE

Parent Feedback Form

Parent Feedback Form

2019

BPT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	70%	10%	10%		
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	20%	20%	10%	
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	40%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	10%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	40%	20%	10%	10%	
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	30%		
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	20%		
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	20%	10%	

A handwritten signature in purple ink, appearing to be 'Allu', written over a horizontal line.

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MANGALORE

How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given placements?
 system in the College?
 achieved from the courses?
 How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the...
 How do you rate the programmes based on the
 How do rate the courses in terms of
 How do you rate the ambience of the college
 How do you rate the treatment of the students by...
 How do you rate the quality and relevance of the
 How do you rate the availability of the text and
 How do you rate the programme that your ward...

Parent Feedback Form

2020

BPT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	70%	10%	10%		
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	60%	20%	20%		
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	40%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	10%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	50%	30%	10%		
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	30%		
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	20%		
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	20%	20%		
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	20%	20%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	30%	10%	

A handwritten signature in purple ink, appearing to be 'Allu', written over a horizontal line.

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Parent Feedback Form

2021

BPT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	70%	10%	10%		
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	20%	20%	10%	
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	40%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	10%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	40%	20%	10%	10%	
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	30%		
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	20%		
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	20%	10%	

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MANGALORE

Parent Feedback Form

2021

MPT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses indifferent semesters?	50%	50%			
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	30%	20%		
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	50%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	30%			
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	40%	30%	30%		
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	65%	10%	20%	5%	
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	70%	30%			
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	50%	30%	20%		
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	70%	10%	20%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	40%	20%	20%	10%	

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MANGALORE

Parent Feedback Form

2020

MPT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	70%	10%	10%		
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	50%	20%	20%	10%	
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	40%	30%	10%	10%	
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	10%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	40%	20%	10%	10%	
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	60%	10%	30%		
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	60%	20%	20%		
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	60%	10%	20%	10%	
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	60%	20%	10%	10%	
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	60%	20%	20%		

A handwritten signature in purple ink, appearing to be 'Allu V', written over a faint circular stamp.

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MANGALORE

Parent Feedback Form

2019

MPT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses indifferent semesters?	60%	30%	10%		
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	70%	30%			
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	60%	40%			
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	20%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	30%	10%		
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	20%	10%		
7	How do you rate the programs based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	70%	20%	10%		
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	30%	10%		
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	70%	20%	10%		
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	70%	20%	10%		
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	50%	30%	20%		

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MANGALORE

Parent Feedback Form

2018

MPT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the program that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses indifferent semesters?		100%			
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?		100%			
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?		100%			
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	100%				
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?		100%			
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?		100%			
7	How do you rate the programs based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?		100%			
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	100%				
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?		100%			
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?		100%			
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?			100%		
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?		100%			
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college		100%			

A handwritten signature in purple ink, appearing to be 'Srinivas'.

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MANGALORE

How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given placements?

system in the College?

achieved from the courses?

How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the...

How do you rate the programs based on the

How do rate the courses in terms of

How do you rate the ambience of the college for...

How do you rate the treatment of the students by...

How do you rate the quality and relevance of the

How do you rate the availability of the text and

How do you rate the program that your ward

Parent Feedback Form

2017

MPT

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses indifferent semesters?	60%	30%	10%		
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	70%	30%			
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	60%	40%			
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	70%	20%	10%		
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	60%	30%	10%		
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	70%	20%	10%		
7	How do you rate the programs based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	70%	20%	10%		
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	70%	20%	10%		
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	60%	30%	10%		
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	70%	20%	10%		
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	70%	20%	10%		
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	60%	30%	10%		
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	50%	30%	20%		

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

**Parents feedback analysis
2017
BHMCT**

Parents ' feedback 2017 BHMCT	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	64	17	4
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	24	35	32	9	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	66	23	11	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	0	15	18	45	22
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	26	35	39	0	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	10	25	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	18	35	40	7	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	18	28	45	4
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	2	21	25	35	17
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	18	38	30	14	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	12	18	40	30

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MANGALORE

Parents feedback analysis

**SRINIVAS
UNIVERSITY**
Parents feedback analysis
2018
BHMCT

Parents ' feedback 2018 BHMCT	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	64	17	4
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	24	35	32	9	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	66	23	11	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	0	15	18	45	22
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	26	35	39	0	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	10	25	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	18	35	40	7	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	18	28	45	4
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	2	21	25	35	17
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	18	38	30	14	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	12	18	40	30

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MANGALORE

**Parents feedback analysis
2019
BHMCT**

Parents ' feedback 2019 BHMCT	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	15	25	30	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	35	30	25	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	15	30	25	25	05
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	25	35	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	20	25	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	35	20	35	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	40	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	35	5
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	15	35	30	20	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	35	15

**REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE**

**Parents feedback analysis
2020
BHMCT**

Parents ' feedback 2020 BHMCT

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	30	25	35	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	25	35	20	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	30	35	30	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	15	35	25	20	05
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	30	25	30	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	20	25	30	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	25	35	15	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	15	25	35	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	10	25	35	30	0
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	15	35	30	20	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	25	45	15

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**Parents feedback analysis
2021
BHMCT**

Parents ' feedback 2021 BHMCT	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	15	25	25	35	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	30	25	30	15	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	15	25	25	30	05
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	25	35	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	20	25	35	20	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	20	45	30	5	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	35	10	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	30	35	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	10	30	35	25	0
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	25	25	35	15

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Parents feedback analysis

**Parents feedback analysis
2017
B.Sc. (H)**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	64	17	4
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	24	35	32	9	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	66	23	11	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	0	15	18	45	22
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	26	35	39	0	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	10	25	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	18	35	40	7	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	18	28	45	4
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	2	21	25	35	17
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	18	38	30	14	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	12	18	40	30

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Parents feedback analysis

**Parents feedback analysis
2018
B.Sc. (H)**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	64	17	4
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	24	35	32	9	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	66	23	11	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	0	15	18	45	22
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	26	35	39	0	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	10	25	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	18	35	40	7	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	18	28	45	4
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	2	21	25	35	17
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	18	38	30	14	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	12	18	40	30

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Parents feedback analysis
2019
B.Sc. (H)

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	15	25	30	30	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	35	30	25	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	15	30	25	25	05
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	25	35	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	20	25	25	25	5
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	35	20	35	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	25	40	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	5	25	30	35	5
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	15	35	30	20	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	35	35	15

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Parents feedback analysis

2021

Nursing Science

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	80%	12%	8%	0%	0%
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	75%	20%	5%	0%	0%
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	70%	15%	12%	3%	0%
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	85%	12%	3%	0%	0%
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	85%	10%	3%	1%	1%
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	85%	8%	4%	3%	0%
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	75%	12%	7%	4%	2%
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	85%	8%	4%	3%	0%
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	80%	15%	2%	1%	2%
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	15%	4%	0%	1%
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	75%	10%	10%	3%	2%
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	80%	12%	7%	1%	0%
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	75%	15%	5%	3%	2%

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Parents feedback analysis

2020

Nursing Science

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	80%	10%	8%	1%	1%
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	75%	15%	5%	3%	2%
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	70%	15%	12%	3%	0%
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	85%	12%	3%	0%	0%
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	85%	10%	3%	1%	1%
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	85%	8%	4%	3%	0%
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	75%	12%	7%	4%	2%
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	85%	8%	4%	3%	0%
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	80%	15%	2%	1%	2%
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	15%	4%	0%	1%
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	85%	10%	2%	2%	1%
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	85%	12%	22%	1%	0%
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	75%	15%	7%	3%	0%

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Parents feedback analysis

2019

Nursing Science

Sl.No	How satisfied are you with the overall system	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
1	How do you rate the programme that your ward undergoing in terms of the load of the courses in different semesters?	80%	10%	8%	1%	1%
2	How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	75%	15%	5%	3%	2%
3	How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	70%	15%	12%	3%	0%
4	How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	85%	12%	3%	0%	0%
5	How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	85%	10%	3%	1%	1%
6	How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	85%	8%	4%	3%	0%
7	How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	75%	12%	7%	4%	2%
8	How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	85%	8%	4%	3%	0%
9	How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	80%	15%	2%	1%	2%
10	How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	80%	15%	4%	0%	1%
11	How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	85%	10%	2%	2%	1%
12	How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	85%	12%	22%	1%	0%
13	How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	75%	15%	7%	3%	0%

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Parents feedback analysis

**SRINIVAS
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**Parents feedback analysis
2021
B.Ed**

Parents Feedback B.Ed. 2021 Batch	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	64	17	4
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	24	35	32	9	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	66	23	11	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	0	15	18	45	22
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	26	35	39	0	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	10	25	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	18	35	40	7	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	18	28	45	4
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	2	21	25	35	17
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	18	38	30	14	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	12	18	40	30

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Parents feedback analysis

Parents feedback analysis

2020

B.Ed

Parents Feedback B.Ed. 2020 Batch	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	64	17	4
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	24	35	32	9	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	66	23	11	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	0	15	18	45	22
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	26	35	39	0	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	10	25	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	18	35	40	7	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	18	28	45	4
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	2	21	25	35	17
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	18	38	30	14	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	12	18	40	30

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**Parents feedback analysis
2019
B.Ed**

Parents Feedback B.Ed. 2019 Batch	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	64	17	4
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	24	35	32	9	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	66	23	11	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	0	15	18	45	22
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	26	35	39	0	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	10	25	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	18	35	40	7	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	18	28	45	4
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	2	21	25	35	17
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	18	38	30	14	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	12	18	40	30

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Parents feedback analysis

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**Parents feedback analysis
2018
B.Ed**

Parents Feedback B.Ed. 2018 Batch	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	0	15	64	17	4
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	24	35	32	9	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	66	23	11	0	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	0	15	18	45	22
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	26	35	39	0	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	10	25	40	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	35	30	10	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	18	35	40	7	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	5	18	28	45	4
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	2	21	25	35	17
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	18	38	30	14	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	12	18	40	30

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Parents feedback analysis

**Parents feedback analysis
2021
B.Sc. (H)**

Parents ' feedback	Very				
	Excellent	Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	15	25	25	35	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	30	25	30	15	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	15	25	25	30	05
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	25	25	35	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	20	25	35	20	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	20	45	30	5	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	35	10	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	10	30	35	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	10	30	35	25	0
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	20	30	35	15	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college.	0	25	25	35	15

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**Parents feedback analysis
2020
B.Sc. (H)**

Parents ' feedback

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor
How do you rate the availability of the text and reference books in the market?	10	30	25	35	0
How do you rate the quality and relevance of the courses included into the curriculum?	25	35	20	10	0
How do you rate the treatment of the students by the faculty irrespective of the background of the student (Gender, cast, community, creed etc.) in teaching and evaluation?	30	35	30	5	0
How do you rate the ambience of the college for effective delivery of the academic process?	15	35	25	20	05
How do rate the courses in terms of their relevance to the latest and/or future technologies?	30	25	30	15	0
How do you rate the programmes based on the comfort of your ward in coping with the workload?	20	25	30	25	0
How do you rate the quality of the teaching in the Institution?	25	25	35	15	0
How do you rate the outcomes that your ward has achieved from the courses?	20	35	30	15	0
How do you rate the transparency of the evaluation system in the College?	15	25	35	20	5
How do you rate the college activities that help your ward in getting jobs and placements?	10	25	35	30	0
How do you rate the transformation of your ward after the completion of the course?	15	35	30	20	0
How do you rate the scholarship/ concessions given to your ward by the college	0	15	25	45	15

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